

ESSENTIAL OIL FROM FLOWERS OF KEWDA (*PANDANUS ODORATISSIMUS*).

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The essential oil from the flowers of *Kewda* contains methyl ether of *β*-phenylethyl alcohol (about 79%), which imparts the attractive fragrance. The ethyl has been synthesised from the alcohol.

An essential oil extract from the flowers of *Kewda* in the Hindusthan Aromatics Laboratories has been described (Sadgopal, *J. Soap Perfumery and Cosmetics*, 1937, 10, 396). An oil (A) isolated from the same source by the present author seems to be different from the former in physical properties and composition.

Oil described by Hindusthan.
Aromatics Laboratory.

n_D^{20} 1.5220
 d_{15}^4 1.0880

and yield per cent. of material
used 0.1 to 0.3

Oil A.

n_D^{18} 1.4950
 d_{18}^4 0.9373

0.06

This difference is probably due to the fact that in the Hindusthan Aromatics laboratory the oil was obtained by extraction with solvents and the fats removed by precipitation with alcohol, whereas the present author obtained it by steam distillation.

15 Kilos of flowers yielded 10 c.c. of the crude oil. On distillation under reduced pressure a small portion (about 30%) passed below 70°/12 mm., but the bulk boiled steadily between 70-74°/12 mm., which on redistillation boiled at 68-70°/12 mm. [Found : C, 80.68 ; H, 9.8, OMe (micro), 18.85. $C_{10}H_{14}O$ requires C, 79.95 ; H, 9.39 ; OMe, 20.64 per cent].

Preliminary experiments showed that this constant boiling fraction contains a small amount of unsaturated impurity. The uptake of hydrogen was about 4% of the value required for one double bond. The same value for unsaturation was obtained by permonophthalic acid titration (Böhme, *Ber.*, 1937, 70, 379).

That the group is methoxy and not higher alkoxy was proved by the interaction of the alkyl halide with silver 3 : 5-dinitrobenzoate and the identification of the product as methyl 3 : 5-dinitrobenzoate.

It was not possible to remove the small amount of unsaturated impurity responsible for divergence between theoretical and analytical data. Dilute permanganate was slowly but continuously reduced by the oil.

On boiling with excess of hydriodic acid for 5 hours the oil gave an iodide (b.p. $90^{\circ}/5$ mm.), which reacted with pyridine and gave a crystalline additive product, m.p. 164° . (Found: C, 49.89; H, 4.23; N, 4.75. $C_{13}H_{14}NI$ requires C, 50.1; H, 4.5; N, 4.5 per cent).

The product is, therefore, $C_{13}H_{14}NI$ and the iodide is C_8H_9I and the oil is mainly the ether C_8H_9OMe or $C_9H_{12}O$ (not $C_{10}H_{14}O$).

Oxidation with permanganate gave benzoic acid. Hence it is either (I) or (II).

(I)

(II)

The iodide (b. p. $90^{\circ}/5$ mm.) reacted with silver 3:5-dinitrobenzoate and gave a substance m.p. 106° , identified as 3:5-dinitrobenzoate of β -phenylethyl alcohol.

Hence the substance has the structure (I) and this was confirmed by its synthesis from β -phenylethyl alcohol. The synthetic methyl ether resembles the Kewda component in physical properties and has the characteristic fragrance of Kewda. It reduces permanganate slowly.

Natural Kewda component.		Synthetic ether having characteristic fragrance of Kewda.
n_D^{20} ...	1.4950	1.4995
n_D^{25} ...	1.4930	1.4970
d_{16}^{20} ...	0.9373	d_{16}^{27} 0.9417
B.p. ...	$182-86^{\circ}/710$ mm.	$185-86^{\circ}/710$ mm.

The composition of the Kewda oil prepared in the Hindusthan Aromatics laboratory has been given as benzyl benzoate, benzyl salicylate, benzyl acetate, benzyl alcohol, geraniol, santalol, linalol, linalyl acetate, bromostyrol, guaiacol, phenylethyl alcohol, but the methyl ether of β -phenylethyl alcohol which constitutes about 79% of the oil has not been stated to occur:

E X P E R I M E N T A L

15 Kilos of the outer part of *kewda* flowers freed from the inner part or pollen, were placed on the upper platform of a copper still charged with 39 litres of water. The condensed steam containing the oil was made to pass in succession through layers of chloroform kept in three bottles at descending levels. The chloroform absorbed most of the oil. Distillation was stopped when 20 litres of water were collected. The chloroform containing the absorbed oil was separated from water and the bulk of the oil was obtained on removal of the solvent. A further small amount was obtained by extracting the water with more chloroform, yield 10 c.c. from which 7 c.c. of the component, b. p. 180° - $85^{\circ}/710$ mm. or 70 - $74^{\circ}/12$ mm. was obtained.

Preparation of the Iodide, C₈H₉I.—To 4 g. of the redistilled component were added hydriodic acid (15 c. c., b. p. 127°). The mixture was refluxed with a little red phosphorus at 150° for 5 hours. After removing the unchanged phosphorus, cold sodium hydroxide solution was added until the mixture was slightly alkaline and the heavy oil which separated was extracted with ether. After washing, drying and removing of the solvent the residual liquid was distilled. A small portion boiled at 80 - $90^{\circ}/5$ mm. but the bulk boiled at $90^{\circ}/5$ mm. The colourless distillate soon acquired red colour due to liberation of iodine.

The iodide reacted with pyridine on warming. The addition product crystallises from alcohol in prisms, m.p. 164° . Analysis, recorded in the introduction, agrees with C₁₃H₁₄NI.

Oxidation of the Oil by Permanganate.

To oil (2 g.) was added in instalments potassium permanganate solution (1%, 700 cc.) and the mixture was gently refluxed until the colour of the permanganate was discharged (4 hours). The filtered liquid which was slightly alkaline was concentrated, acidified and extracted with ether, whence benzoic acid (m. p. and mixed m. p. 120° . Found: C, 68.21; H, 5.23 per cent) was isolated.

3:5 Dinitrobenzoate of phenylethyl alcohol was prepared from 3:5-dinitrobenzoyl chloride and phenylethyl alcohol. Crystallising in plates from alcohol it had m.p. 106° . (Found: N, 9.5. C₁₅H₂₃O₆N₂ requires N, 8.9 per cent). It showed no depression when mixed with the product of interaction of the iodide (b. p. $90^{\circ}/5$ mm.) obtained from the oil and silver dinitrobenzoate in benzene suspension.

Synthesis of the Ether (I).—Methylation with dimethylsulphate in presence of alkali left much of the alcohol unchanged. Unsatisfactory results were obtained by using sodium methylate and methyl iodide in methyl alcoholic solution. When, however, phenylethyl alcohol (1 mol.) was gently refluxed for 6 hours with methyl iodide (3 mols) and silver oxide (1½ mol.) it was quantitatively methylated. The ether could be distilled without decomposition at ordinary pressure, b. p. 185-86°/710 mm. It is this ether which imparts the attractive fragrance to kewda.

Hammonst (*Compt. rend.*, 1901, 138, 814) obtained this ether by interaction of benzylmagnesium bromide with bromomethyl ether, b. p. 189°/760 mm., but prepared in this way it could not be freed from bromo compounds.

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